

Hypothesis Testing in Adaptively Randomized Experiments: Using the Allocation Probabilities for Inference

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Abstract: Adaptive experiments are increasingly being used in many fields including education to improve learning experiences and instructional strategies. Compared to traditional randomized control experiments, adaptive experiments allow for more dynamic data collection procedures based on real-time accumulating data. This makes them ideal in situations where a balance of exploration and exploitation is needed to optimize decision making and outcomes. However, the analysis and inference of data from such adaptive methods, especially those using bandit algorithms, remains a challenging task. In particular, this paper addresses the problem of hypothesis testing. We discuss a novel approach to testing, based on the allocation probabilities of the underlying design. Then, we explore alternative variants of this allocation probability test and examine their behavior in different experimental settings with varying sample sizes and base success rates.

Keywords: Adaptive experiments, Hypothesis testing, Thompson sampling, Bayesian designs

1 Introduction

Randomized controlled experiments are fundamental in evaluating the effectiveness of treatments in various fields [16]. They offer solid theoretical guarantees [11], yet these experiments can pose financial, temporal, and operational challenges [9]. Consequently, adaptively randomized experiments have been introduced as an alternative. In this approach, the collection of new data is influenced by previously acquired data, offering a more time-efficient way of conducting the experiment with goals such as maximizing the outcome of interest.

Multi-armed bandit (MAB) algorithms have been recognized for decades as a powerful tool for adaptive experiments [15]. Within an MAB framework, the algorithm dynamically allocates treatments (or ‘arms’) to participants, aiming to maximize the assignment of higher-outcome arms to a larger participant group. For instance, in an educational setting, arms might represent different versions of hints in an online homework assignment, with the reward being the correct solution of a subsequent question post-hint reception. Through MAB algorithms, the adaptive experiment tries to identify the most effective version of hints while ensuring participants receive optimal benefits.

The adoption of bandit algorithms has faced multiple barriers, primarily due to the uncertainty in evaluating the effectiveness of treatments throughout the experiment [14]. Theoretical analyses of hypothesis testing suggest that such adaptive data collection can induce biases in the estimates of treatments and broaden the constructed confidence intervals due to the imbalance between sample sizes [10]. However, it has been observed that there are issues with an inflated false positive rate (FPR), which can further impact practical decisions and scientific research, contributing to the “replication crisis” in social and behavioral sciences [12].

In the context of hypothesis testing on data collected through bandit algorithms, classical statistical procedures and tests may lead to reduced power compared to traditional A/B testing. Previous

studies have found that even when treatment effects across the population are similar, traditional bandit algorithms like Thompson Sampling (TS) [17] may overly allocate observations to one arm over the other[19], thereby reducing the statistical power for comparative analysis. While common population comparison methods such as the Wald-Z test assess the data offline by dividing it into separate groups, they generally assume that the data collection process is independent. However, this assumption does not fully hold in adaptive experiments, where data is collected sequentially and adaptively based on prior treatment allocations and observed outcomes. Consequently, the independence assumption between outcomes is valid only conditionally on past results, but does not apply unconditionally.

Furthermore, due to the adaptive nature of conducting such experiments, it is inevitable that sample sizes within each sub-treatment group will vary across treatments, reducing the probability of correctly detecting differences when using traditional comparison techniques. This often results in an inflated FPR and reduced detection power, a problem potentially worsened by different experimental settings. Therefore, traditional hypothesis testing methods like the Wald-Z test, which treats data from adaptively conducted experiments as offline data, may be insufficient based on these considerations.

In this paper, we build on the Allocation Probability test (AP-test) statistic introduced in[8, 4], taking into account its adaptive nature. We compare its performance across various experimental settings and introduce alternative variants aimed at improving FPR control by incorporating more information from the adaptive process. We begin by describing the methods, including the experimental setup for our simulation, as well as the policies for how treatments are allocated across different arms. Next, we present the AP-test in three formats: discrete, continuous, and continuous that adapts to non-lenient probabilities. We then examine the results of our simulations and compare the three versions of the AP-test. The discussion section focuses on potential extensions of the methodology and the theoretical challenges associated with using these test statistics.

2 Experimental Setup and the Bandit Framework

We consider a stochastic bandit framework [2, 3], where the problem can be defined as follows. Let K be the number of arms of a slot machine (the bandit). At each time step $t = 1, \dots, N$, one of the K arms is pulled and a reward or outcome is obtained according to a fixed (but unknown) distribution. In the stochastic framework, the rewards obtained from repeated plays, denoted by $r_t, t = 1, \dots, N$, are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.).

An algorithm in the MAB problem must decide which arm to play at each time step t , based on the outcome of the previous $t - 1$ plays. Let $i(t)$ denote the arm played at time t , and let θ_i represent the unknown expected reward for arm i . The maximum expected reward across all arms is given by $\theta^* := \max_i \theta_i$. The regret associated with the selection of arm i at any time t is defined as $\Delta_i := \theta^* - \theta_i$. The number of times that arm i has been played up to step $t - 1$ is denoted by $k_i(t)$.

For simplicity of exposition, in the rest of this paper, we will focus on a two-armed setting with $K = 2$, where arm 1 denotes the experimental treatment and arm 2 is the control treatment. We will also assume binary rewards for each arm, i.e., $r_t \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\theta_i)$, with $\theta_i \in [0, 1]$ representing the probability of observing a success, for $i = 1, 2$. In such a case, we will also use $\{s_i^t, f_i^t\} \in \mathcal{S}^t$ to denote the cumulative counts of successes and failures for the Bernoulli trials of arm i at time t , where \mathcal{S}^t is the state space (joint list) of the possible successes and failures of all arms at time t .

2.1 Thompson Sampling

Thompson Sampling (TS) is a commonly used randomized MAB algorithm for reward-maximizing experiments framed under a Bayesian setting. In cases with binary rewards, a Bernoulli model with unknown success parameter θ_i for each arm i is typically used to model the rewards. To allow for model conjugacy, therefore feasible exact computations, a Beta distribution is used as the prior distribution for θ_i ; this allows us to estimate, inferring from the data, the effectiveness (success probability) of each treatment at each time t , by $\hat{\theta}_{i,t}$. In our setup, we assume independent Beta-distributed priors with parameters $\alpha_i = 1$ and $\beta_i = 1$, which correspond to a uniform distribution.

At each iteration of TS, a sample is drawn from the posterior distribution of θ_i (which is a Beta distribution due to its conjugacy) for each arm, and the arm with the largest sampled value is pulled. Within each run $t = 1, \dots, N$, one arm is selected, and an outcome of 0 (failure) or 1 (success) is recorded. The beliefs about the unknown reward distribution parameters (posterior) are then updated, and the next patient is allocated to a treatment based on the updated belief. The success rate for each arm i at time t is estimated based on empirical results as:

$$\text{Posterior Belief of } \theta_i \text{ at } t: \theta_{i,t} \sim \text{Beta}(s_i^t + 1, f_i^t + 1), \quad i = 1, 2.$$

TS balances exploration and exploitation over time, and it is theoretically guaranteed to converge to the optimal arm as $t \rightarrow \infty$, if an optimal arm, i.e., one with a highest reward, exists [1]. If two arms have the same expected reward, choosing either arm is equivalent for reward maximization, making both arms optimal. Under the arm-equivalence setting, there are no theoretical guarantees on the convergence of TS and TS may diverge towards or predominantly select one of the arms.

TS represents a well-studied policy for running adaptive experiments, as opposed to traditional (fixed) randomized experiments. For the latter, uniform random (UR) is used as a baseline policy in which participants are assigned to treatments with equal probability. In a two-arm setting, this approach emulates a traditional A/B test, with treatment groups A and B each receiving a 50% allocation rate among the participant population. The main difference between TS and UR is in the way treatments are assigned to participants. When there is an actual difference in the success rates of the arms, the UR policy will not use this information to skew the allocations, thus yielding a lower average reward compared to a reward-maximizing policy. However, UR is complemented with strong statistical properties and robust inference [19].

3 Hypothesis Testing and the Allocation Probability Test

The problem we tackle in this work is hypothesis testing, with a focus on a one-tailed test evaluating whether the experimental arm (arm 1) is superior to the control arm (arm 2), i.e.,

$$H_0 : \theta_1 = \theta_2 \quad \text{vs.} \quad H_1 : \theta_1 > \theta_2.$$

One way to perform this task is through the use of a test statistic, which is then evaluated on the basis of its corresponding false positive rate (FPR) and Power. Specifically, in this section, we investigate a novel test statistic, the Allocation Probability Test (AP-test) [8]. We outline its original discrete form and discuss alternative continuous variants.

We remind that Power is defined as $1 - \beta$, where β is the Type-II error, and it represents the probability of correctly rejecting the null hypothesis when there is a significant difference between arms. On the other side, the FPR α is the proportion of times the null hypothesis is falsely rejected despite no actual difference in success rates across arms. For simplicity, in this work, we will set the FPR at 10%, though empirical results may vary. While Power and FPR can be easily calculated in a two-arm setting, they become more complex in trials with $K > 2$ arms [18], where Power must be appropriately adapted to multiple hypothesis.

The Discrete Allocation Probability Test The original version of the AP-test statistic [8, 4], is based on the observed number of times the allocation probability of the experimental arm under a pre-specified bandit policy used to collect the data, say p_t , exceeds the one expected under an UR policy. In a two-arm setting, the latter is given by 0.5, and the AP-test at the end of the experiment ($t = N$) is given by:

$$APT_N = \sum_{t=2}^N \mathbf{1}(p_t > 0.5),$$

where the first time step $t = 1$ is disregarded since the allocation probabilities are uniquely informed by the priors. Notably, when these are identical for the two arms, $p_1 = 0.5$.

For a TS policy with binary rewards and Beta priors, where the posterior distribution f of $\theta_i, i = 1, 2$, follows a Beta distribution, the allocation probability of arm 1 at time t —that is, the posterior

probability that arm 1 is optimal—is defined as:

$$p_t = \mathcal{P}(\theta_{1,t} > \theta_{2,t} | s_1^t, s_2^t, f_1^t, f_2^t) = \int_0^1 \int_0^{\theta_{1,t}} f_{\theta_{1,t}}(\theta_{1,t}) f_{\theta_{2,t}}(\theta_{2,t}) d\theta_{2,t} d\theta_{1,t}.$$

Directly computing this integral is complex and we use the result in [13] to approximate it as:

$$p_t = \mathcal{P}(\theta_{1,t} > \theta_{2,t} | s_1^t, s_2^t, f_1^t, f_2^t) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{s_1^t} \frac{B(s_2^t + 1 + i, f_1^t + f_2^t + 2)}{(f_1^t + 1 + i)B(1 + i, f_1^t + 1)B(s_2^t + 1, f_2^t + 1)},$$

with B denoting the Beta function.

Given the discrete nature of the test statistic, its distribution can be computed exactly by determining the mass probability at each individual point of the support in $\{0, 1, \dots, N\}$. The exact distribution is provided in [8] for the TS policy, allowing for the determination of a critical value that would ensure a certain FPR control $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. However, this discrete-based test statistic, similarly to other exact tests such as the Fisher’s test, comes with the drawback of an often too conservative (non-continuous) FPR control. While exact FPR control may be achievable through a randomized decision rule, as illustrated in [8], this approach requires estimating the excess FPR control. Furthermore, since a dichotomization step is involved in the indicator function, this test could result in an important information loss.

A Fully Continuous Allocation Probability Test In the pursuit of an exact FPR control, as well as a complete use of the informative content provided by the allocation probabilities, our first approach is based on working with a fully continuous version of the AP-test. This approach relies on the mean allocation probability of the experimental arm observed throughout the trial, with the continuous AP-test statistic defined as follows:

$$APT_N^{(\text{continuous})} := \frac{\sum_{t=2}^N p_t}{N - 1}.$$

As we will illustrate in Section 4, this version appears effective in the initial stages of testing, under specific sample sizes and effect sizes. However, accumulating all allocation probabilities includes periods when an adaptive policy, such as TS, is still exploring the effectiveness of different treatments. This may result in significant fluctuations of the continuous AP-test over time and introduce unnecessary noise.

Non-lenient Allocation Probability Test Building on the idea of a Lenient Regret framework [5], we now refine the continuous allocation probability approach by evaluating whether changes in allocation probabilities are consistent (non-lenient) enough to support inference, based on a constant tolerance threshold $c \in [0, 1]$. The non-lenient AP-test statistic is defined as follows:

$$APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})} := \frac{\sum_{t=2}^N \mathbf{1}(|p_t - p_{t-1}| \leq c) \cdot p_t}{\sum_{t=2}^N \mathbf{1}(|p_t - p_{t-1}| \leq c)}.$$

Since this metric evaluates the proportion of time the allocation probabilities have stabilized within a certain threshold c , the distribution of this test statistic can be estimated with a higher degree of robustness. Based on our current simulation results, it appears to resemble a uniform shape (or a Beta distribution), under several settings. This will be further discussed in Section 4.

4 Simulation Results

In the following sections, we compare the three versions of the AP-test across a TS and an UR policy. We conduct this comparison within the following simulated educational experimental setting.

Consider a college/university classroom scenario with two classroom sizes: $N = 100$ (small classroom) and $N = 785$ (large classroom). The two treatments are given by arm 1 (the experimental arm, involving an innovative video module explaining statistical concepts to students), and arm 2 (the control arm, consisting of a traditional textbook chapter on the same statistical concepts). We defined the reward based on whether or not students correctly answer a pop-up quiz after completing the module (1 if correct, 0 if not).

The comparison also involves different effect sizes. In the case of two-armed experiments, the effect size is represented by the standard Cohen’s d measure [6], defined as:

$$d = \frac{\theta_2 - \theta_1}{\text{standard deviation of } \tilde{\theta}},$$

where $\tilde{\theta}$ is the pooled success rate, accounting for the sample sizes of the two treatment groups.

For a binary reward scenario, we set the success rates of the two arms centered at 0.5. This assumption allows us to approximate Cohen’s d as $d \approx \frac{\theta_2 - \theta_1}{\text{constant}} \propto \theta_2 - \theta_1$. Specifically, we consider three hypothetical effect sizes for evaluation: 0.0 (indicating no difference between the video and textbook modules), 0.1 (indicating a small effect of the video module), and 0.2 (indicating a moderate effect). These effect sizes allow us to assess the FPR (when the effect size is 0.0) and the power (when the effect sizes are 0.1 or 0.2). Note that the sample size of $N = 785$ is chosen to achieve 80% power at a significance level of 0.05 under the UR policy with an effect size of 0.2.

Discrete Allocation Probability Test Starting with the APT_N test in its discrete version, we first illustrate the distribution of this test statistic under the null ($H_0 : \theta_1 = \theta_2$) and alternative hypotheses ($H_1 : \theta_1 > \theta_2$) in a small classroom setting where $N = 100$; these are shown in Figure 1.

Several observations arise from this plot. First, with a small classroom, the test statistic is observably discrete due to the summation of indicator events at each time point. This discreteness results in an empirical, non-exact FPR control of 8.6% at the critical value (CV) of 97, determined so as to ensure a FPR control of $\alpha = 10\%$. This translates into a power of 18.8% and 29.7% for effect sizes of 0.1 and 0.2, respectively, based on 20,000 simulations.

Figure 1: Distribution of the discrete APT_N test for different effect sizes $\theta_1 - \theta_2$ of 0, 0.1, and 0.2. The nominal level is set to $\alpha = 10\%$, controlled at a Critical Value (CV) of 97 (dashed vertical line) for $N = 100$.

With an increase in sample size to a large classroom setting of $N = 785$, we achieve a more accurate and exact FPR of 9.9% at $CV = 775$. Consequently, the power is observed to be 37.9% and 62.6% for effect sizes of 0.1 and 0.2, respectively, based on a total of 20,000 simulations.

In comparing the two classroom size settings with $N = 100$ and $N = 785$, we observe that the FPR under the null hypothesis is well-controlled at the pre-specified 10% nominal level. With the

larger classroom size, the FPR control is closer to the nominal value (8.6% vs. 9.9%). Furthermore, the power achieved for the two classroom sizes under the alternative hypothesis increases as classroom size or treatment effect size increases, aligning with traditional hypothesis testing techniques.

Further comparing the performance of the TS policy with the traditional randomized controlled UR policy, we present the combined results for both classroom settings in Table [1].

Table 1: Comparison of TS and UR Policies for Different Sample Sizes Using the Discrete AP Test Over 20,000 Simulations

Effect Size	Average Reward TS	Students on Correct Treatment TS	Students on Correct Treatment UR	Discrete AP Test FPR/Power N = 100	Discrete AP test FPR/Power N = 785
0.0	0.50	50%	50%	8.6%	9.9%
0.1	0.52	67%	50%	18.8%	37.9%
0.2	0.56	79%	50%	29.7%	62.6%

Cross-comparing the policies, these results suggest that the TS approach significantly outperforms in terms of correct treatment allocation rate across simulations. Moreover, the reward (outcome) for students in the TS policy group is, on average, better than that of the UR policy. This finding is particularly valuable in educational and health settings, where participant rewards (often as benefits) are also critical to the experiment.

Fully Continuous Allocation Probability Test Using the fully continuous version of the test $APT_N^{(\text{continuous})}$, under the same classroom and treatment effect settings as before, we observe now a more continuous distribution of the test under the null and alternative hypotheses; these are shown in Figure 2 for a classroom size of $N = 100$.

Figure 2: Distribution of the continuous $APT_N^{(\text{continuous})}$ test for $N = 100$ for different effect sizes $\theta_1 - \theta_2$ of 0, 0.1, and 0.2 over 20,000 simulations.. The nominal level is set to $\alpha = 10\%$, controlled at a Critical Value (CV) of 0.858 (dashed vertical line) for $N = 100$.

For $N = 100$ with a nominal level set at $\alpha = 10\%$, the CV is given by 0.858 and achieves an exact 10.0% FPR control, with a power of 25.0% for an effect size of 0.1 and 48.8% for an effect size of 0.2. Similarly, for $N = 785$, the CV is given by 0.887 with an exact 10.0% FPR control and a power of 56.3% for an effect size of 0.1 and 93.7% for an effect size of 0.2.

These results show that, for both classroom sizes, the continuous AP test offers a more precise FPR control compared to the discrete version. Additionally, the power to detect the module’s effect size increases substantially while maintaining the expected behavior in traditional test statistics: as sample size increases, the power to detect effects also increases.

Non-Lenient Allocation Probability Test We extend the comparison to the proposed non-lenient $APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})}$ testing framework. With classroom sizes of $N = 100$ and $N = 785$, and a tuned threshold of $c = 0.05$ (representing the tolerance for fluctuations in a stabilized, or non-lenient, allocation probability), we can observe a distribution for the test statistics as described in Figure [3], which presents the distributions of the test under the null and alternative hypotheses for $N = 785$.

Figure 3: Distribution of the continuous non-lenient $APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})}$ test for $N = 785$ across different effect sizes $\theta_1 - \theta_2$ of 0, 0.1, and 0.2. The nominal level is set to $\alpha = 10\%$, controlled at a Critical Value (CV) of 0.884 (dashed vertical line) for $N = 758$.

For a large classroom size $N = 785$ (where the critical value under the null hypothesis is 0.884), the power is 57.3% for a small effect of video module (0.1) and 94.5% for a moderate effect of the video module (0.2). For a small classroom setting, $N = 100$, we have a 10% False Positive Rate (critical value of 0.867), a power of 25.1% for an effect size of 0.1 and 47.6% for an effect size of 0.2.

Looking at the three test statistics together in Table 2 for $N = 100$ and Table 3 for $N = 785$, we observe that both continuous AP-test formats outperform the discrete AP-test. This occurs primarily because both types of continuous test statistics preserve more information about the underlying data [7], without any dichotomization/distretization procedure. Nonetheless, we also emphasize that the discrete AP test could yield better performance if the starting time were further optimized [8].

In contrast, the performance of the fully continuous AP-test is comparable to that of the non-lenient AP-test. This is due to several factors: while the non-lenient AP-test is designed to filter out allocation probabilities from the exploration phase of the TS policy, a fixed threshold of $c = 0.05$ may not be optimal. Additionally, the fully continuous AP-test may introduce implicit noises due to early-stage AP fluctuations, while the non-lenient AP test has higher variance due to the fixed threshold c and the indicator-weighted average.

Table 2: Comparison of different AP test statistics for $N = 100$ over 20,000 simulations.

Test Statistics	False Positive Rate ($\theta_1 = \theta_2 = 0.5$)	Power ($\theta_1 = 0.55, \theta_2 = 0.45$)	Power ($\theta_1 = 0.6, \theta_2 = 0.4$)
Discrete Allocation Probability Test	8.6%	18.8%	29.7%
Fully Continuous Allocation Probability Test	10%	25.0%	48.8%
Non-Lenient Allocation Probability Test	10%	25.1%	47.6%

Table 3: Comparison of different AP test statistics for $N = 785$ over 20,000 simulatons.

Test Statistics	False Positive Rate ($\theta_1 = \theta_2 = 0.5$)	Power ($\theta_1 = 0.55, \theta_2 = 0.45$)	Power ($\theta_1 = 0.6, \theta_2 = 0.4$)
Discrete Allocation Probability Test	9.9%	37.9%	62.6%
Fully Continuous Allocation Probability Test	10%	56.3%	93.7%
Non-Lenient Allocation Probability Test	10%	57.3%	94.5%

4.1 Further Investigation of the Null Hypothesis Distribution for $APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})}$

We now focus on the $APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})}$ test and further investigate its distribution under the null hypothesis. Under some values of the threshold parameter c , the distribution of the $APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})}$ test statistic under the null hypothesis resembles a Uniform(0, 1) distribution or, alternatively, a Beta mixture model.

The behavior of the null hypothesis distribution for different c values is shown in Figure 4. We can observe that varying c values lead to distinct $APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})}$ distributions under the null hypothesis. When c is set too low (e.g., $c = 0.01$), only extreme allocation probabilities are captured. This means that only 'bad luck' cases—where TS explores one arm and happens to encounter multiple failures, significantly biasing the treatment estimate—are represented, resulting in a bimodal distribution. As c increases, this bimodal shape diminishes. However, if c becomes too large, indicating an overly lenient tolerance, the distribution begins to show fluctuations.

Another key observation is that the null hypothesis distribution, while sensitive to different c values, remains consistent in both shape and symmetry across various null hypothesis settings (i.e., different $\theta_1 = \theta_2$ values). This consistency is not observed in the fully continuous or discrete cases [8].

Figure 4: Distribution of $APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})}$ over 20,000 simulations under different null hypothesis settings for $N = 785$ with varying c values from (a) to (d).

To better understand the behaviour of the AP-test and its distribution, we examine how the allocation probability under the null hypothesis ($\theta_1 = \theta_2$) changes over time. This is shown in Figure 5 for sample sizes $N = 100$ and $N = 785$.

We observe that the variability of the allocation probabilities generally decreases over time, while the actual fluctuations remain centered around 0.5 under the null hypothesis. This observation, along with the empirical results in Figure 4, leads us to conjecture that the null hypothesis distribution of the non-lenient AP test statistic may follow a Uniform(0, 1) distribution. Using the same setup ($c = 0.05$) as above, we compare the null hypothesis distribution with a Uniform(0, 1) distribution via a QQ-plot, shown in Figure [6].

At first glance, the distribution appears uniform, which is also supported by the QQ-plot. Interestingly, using a Kolmogorov-Smirnov one-sample test for uniformity on $APT_N^{(\text{non-lenient})}$, we found significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis of uniformity for both $N = 100$ (with $D = 0.041796$ and $p < 0.001$) and $N = 785$ (with $D = 0.02$ and $p = 0.034$), based on 20,000

Figure 5: Allocation probability over time for sample sizes $N = 100$ (left) and $N = 785$ (right). Shaded regions represent the 95% confidence intervals based on 20,000 simulations. The figures also display the standard deviation at each time step, highlighting the variation in the allocation probability across the two sample sizes.

Figure 6: Q-Q Plot comparing the empirical distribution of the $APT_N^{(non-lenient)}$ under the null hypothesis ($\theta_1 = \theta_2$) to the theoretical Uniform(0,1) distribution, for sample sizes of $N = 100$ (left) and $N = 785$ (right).

simulations. This result is partially influenced by the large simulation size (20,000), where even small deviations from the uniform distribution yield very low p-values. However, the general trend indicates that the p-value decreases as classroom size increases, suggesting a closer approximation to a Uniform(0, 1) distribution as classroom size grows.

5 Discussion and Conclusions

In this paper, we built on a novel hypothesis testing scheme, the Allocation Probability test (AP-test) [8, 4], and extended it to fully continuous and non-lenient continuous versions, with the goal of achieving improved FPR control and Power. An in-depth analysis was provided on various evaluation metrics, including FPR, power, reward, and correct allocation ratio. The evaluation considered the three formats of this novel AP-test statistic based on a bandit policy’s allocation probabilities: discrete, continuous, and continuous with non-lenient adaptivity.

Using an education-based simulation example, we show-cased how a continuous AP test can potentially improve FPR control and enhance power compared to the original discrete test statistic. Nonetheless, while these test statistics adapt the sequential nature of information gathering throughout the experiment, they also face certain limitations:

- **Absence of a theoretical distribution under the null for the continuous AP-tests** Although we observed that the test statistics resembles a uniform distribution in various scenarios, a rigorous proof remains challenging, and the resulting distribution could indeed be a Beta mixture model. Consequently, the critical value in the continuous AP test is, at this stage, only empirically determined. Furthermore, a uniform distribution, being flat, differs significantly from

the traditional bell-shaped distributions often used in inference-making. This flat shape may be less optimal for hypothesis testing since it provides a narrower rejection region compared to bell-shaped distributions, where more data naturally concentrates in the tails.

- **A fixed threshold of c introduces biases:** As discussed, the non-lenient concept is to filter out initial exploration phases, making the allocation probabilities more reliable for inference. However, using a fixed threshold c as a cutoff for the indicator function may potentially introduce bias and/or cause information loss. This is because a rigid cutoff does not adapt to the natural variability in the data, potentially filtering out allocation probabilities that would otherwise contribute to a more accurate inference.

Given these considerations, we plan to further investigate solutions for the converging distribution of the continuous versions of the AP-test introduced in this work. Furthermore, we aim to identify a soft threshold—potentially inversely related to the remaining time horizon in the trial—that could theoretically support convergence of the test statistic distribution under both null and alternative hypotheses. Finally, extending this framework to multi-treatment comparisons and exploring two-tailed hypothesis testing remain open areas, which we hope to address in future work.

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